

LEGAL REGULATION OF BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract: This article provides detailed information on all areas where blockchain technology can be used by governments, with a detailed explanation of the legal-normative framework and regulation. In addition, ways to encourage blockchain innovation and proposals for a new EU law are provided.

Keywords: Smart contracts, blockchain innovation, crypto-assets.

Introduction. While blockchain technology has penetrated into almost every industry, every entrepreneur or businessman who wants to start his business may have one question, is this technology itself legal, who or what is it subject to, mainly under whose control is it implemented? and others. Of course, these are very relevant questions, if we start from the fact that the main goal of any legal regulation is to ensure the interests of society and the state, to increase the efficiency or to optimize the activity of state institutions, in other words, the goal of legal regulation is to solve the problem consists of solving or obtaining a common benefit. Legal regulation of blockchain technology varies by jurisdiction and is still evolving as governments and regulators struggle to understand and adapt to its implications. No one controls the blockchain, all calculations are managed and controlled by an automated system; actions such as falsifying elections, deceiving the court system, falsifying documents or impersonating another person are not allowed. Blockchain is also called "World Wide Ledger" and "Valuable Ledger". Owners' rights are transparent and reinforced. Transaction

timing and PKI not only prevent double spending, but also record ownership of every bitcoin on the network. Apart from Bitcoin, it can be anything of value, including intellectual property. Initially, blockchain technology was widely used in the financial and banking sectors. Currently, the fields of application of this technology are directly related to the development of social relations. Blockchain technology provides security to intellectual property owners and strong protection against copyright infringers, including potential hackers, who seek to gain access to the digital asset. Blockchain technology is a tool that serves to protect and protect intellectual property objects in telecommunication networks, to limit and prevent unauthorized use by third parties.

Analysis and results. Since the main function of this technology is a method of storing information, any type of information, including digital and digitized information, can be stored in the form of a chain. Blockchain technologies play an important role in the life of society in terms of the efficiency and security of information storage. The introduction of blockchain into the unified electronic registry system of Uzbekistan is part of the project "Improvement and management of public services in rural areas of Uzbekistan" funded by the European Union and implemented in cooperation with the United Nations Development Program in Uzbekistan (UNDP) and the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is one of the measures implemented in order to improve the life of citizens by improving security and speeding up the use of public services within the framework of the IPSD project. Some key legal considerations related to blockchain regulation:

Smart contracts and legal validity - One of the challenges in legal regulation is determining the legal validity of smart contracts. While smart contracts are self-executing and automated, questions may arise as to whether they meet the legal requirements for enforceable contracts in some jurisdictions.

Data privacy and protection - Blockchain's transparency and immutability

may conflict with data privacy regulations, such as the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Striking a balance between the benefits of blockchain and compliance with data protection laws is a complex issue.

AML and KYC Compliance – Anti-Money Laundering (AML) and Know Your Customer (KYC) regulations are important when dealing with blockchain and cryptocurrencies, especially in the context of initial coin offerings (ICOs) and token sales.

Securities Regulations - By their nature, certain cryptocurrencies or tokens may be classified as securities subject to securities regulations. Regulators are working to determine which tokens fall under these classifications.

Tax - The taxation of cryptocurrencies varies by jurisdiction. Governments are grappling with how to tax cryptocurrency transactions, capital gains and income.

Consumer Protection - Consumer protection is an important concern, especially with the rise of ICOs and investment scams. Regulatory bodies seek to protect consumers from potential risks associated with blockchain-based investments.

Intellectual Property and Patents - The legal implications of intellectual property and patents in the context of blockchain technology and smart contracts are complex and evolving. Issues related to ownership, licensing and infringement are being resolved on the basis of legislation.

Cross-Border Transactions and Jurisdiction – The decentralized nature of blockchain technology may present challenges related to determining appropriate jurisdiction for legal disputes and regulatory oversight, particularly in cross-border transactions.

Smart Property and Legal Ownership - Using blockchain to tokenize and transfer ownership of physical assets raises questions about legal ownership and property rights, especially when assets are represented digitally.

Digital signature and identity verification - Legal recognition and identity verification of electronic digital signatures conducted on the Blockchain is an important aspect of legal regulation.

Given the complex and rapidly evolving nature of blockchain technology, governments and regulators are working to develop comprehensive legal frameworks that balance the potential benefits of blockchain with the need for consumer protection, security, and compliance with applicable laws. Legal professionals, policymakers and industry stakeholders are actively working together to create regulations that support innovation in addressing potential risks and challenges. According to information from September 2021, Uzbekistan has taken measures to regulate blockchain and cryptocurrencies within its jurisdiction. However, remember that rules and laws can change and may have changed since then. Below is an overview of the legal regulation of blockchain in Uzbekistan as of September 2021:

Cryptocurrency Legalization:

In 2018, the President of Uzbekistan signed a decree legalizing cryptocurrency trading and creating a legal framework for blockchain and crypto-related activities. The decree recognized cryptocurrencies as assets, allowing individuals and businesses to engage in cryptocurrency trading and other related activities.

Licensing and Regulation:

The 2018 decree also introduced licensing requirements from relevant authorities for cryptocurrency exchanges and other crypto-related businesses. The aim was to ensure proper monitoring and compliance with Anti-Money Laundering (AML) and Know Your Customer (KYC) regulations.

National Blockchain Development Strategy:

In 2018, Uzbekistan announced a national strategy for the development of blockchain technology. The strategy aims to facilitate the implementation of

blockchain technology in various sectors, including public services, agriculture, education and finance.

Tax:

Cryptocurrency transactions are taxed in accordance with current tax legislation in Uzbekistan. At the same time, there have been discussions about the introduction of more precise tax rules for cryptocurrencies.

Digital Trust Agency:

The Digital Trust Agency was established to oversee and regulate digital signature services related to blockchain technology applications.

Promoting Blockchain Innovation:

The government of Uzbekistan has expressed its intention to create a favorable environment for blockchain and technological innovation by encouraging the development of startups and technologies.

It is important to keep up to date with the latest regulations and developments in Uzbekistan, as the legal landscape for blockchain and cryptocurrencies may change over time. If you want the most up-to-date and accurate information on the legal regulation of blockchain in Uzbekistan, I recommend consulting official government sources, lawyers or regulatory agencies in the country. Of course, I can give you general information about the use of cryptocurrency in Uzbekistan, its security, methods of application, advantages, disadvantages, suggestions, conclusions and potential solutions. Now, if we touch on the legal and regulatory basis of the blockchain, we will get more important and necessary information for ourselves.

Legal and regulatory framework for blockchain The European Commission recognizes the importance of legal certainty and a clear regulatory regime in areas related to blockchain-based applications. The EU strongly supports EU-wide regulations for blockchain to avoid legal and regulatory fragmentation. The commission has adopted a comprehensive package of legislative proposals to

regulate crypto-assets to boost investment and protect consumers and investors. This package updates certain financial market rules for crypto-assets and creates a legal framework for the regulatory sandbox of financial supervisors in the EU for the use of blockchains in securities trading and post-trade. The services of the European Central Bank (ECB) and the European Commission are jointly considering a wide range of policy, legal and technical issues related to the implementation of the digital euro. They are considering this in the context of the respective mandates and independence provided for in the Treaties. A joint statement from the European Commission and the ECB outlined cooperation on the digital euro.

Proposal for a new EU law on crypto-assets

Cryptoassets, classified as "financial instruments" under the Market in Financial Instruments Directive, were previously subject to EU securities market legislation. However, these rules predate crypto-assets and DLT. This can hinder innovation. Thus, the Commission proposed a pilot regime for market infrastructures wishing to trade and settle transactions in financial instruments in the form of crypto-assets. The pilot regime allows exemptions from existing regulations and allows regulators and companies to test innovative solutions using blockchain. For crypto-assets that do not fall into the category of "financial instruments", such as utility tokens or payment tokens, the Commission proposed a new system specifically. Market Regulation for Crypto Assets (MiCA) supports innovation while protecting consumers and the integrity of cryptocurrency exchanges. This includes rules such as insider trading or front running. The proposed Regulation covers entities that issue crypto-assets, firms that provide services around these crypto-assets, firms that work with digital wallets, and cryptocurrency exchanges. A pan-European blockchain regulatory sandbox. A sandbox is a facility that brings together regulators, companies and technology experts to test innovative solutions and identify barriers to their adoption. The

European Blockchain Partnership, in collaboration with the European Commission, is planning a pan-European regulatory sandbox for EBSI and non-EBSI use cases, including data migration, business-to-business data spaces, smart contracts and digital identities. This covers health, environment, mobility, energy and other areas. The guide has been expanded and updated since it was first published. Now it's a comprehensive guide to legal and regulatory considerations that everyone in the chain should understand. I think three major changes are imminent. They mean everything a lawyer needs to be familiar with blockchain, smart legal contracts and crypto-assets - both conceptual and functional. These developments are: First, the launch of central bank digital currencies that will put cryptoassets into the mainstream. Second, the widespread adoption of digitally transmitted documents, and third, the transition from analog programs such as Word to intelligent machine-readable documents. This Guidance will put lawyers in a much better position to understand DLT and how smart legal contracts are being created and will soon be used in use cases around the world. Most importantly, it prioritizes English law as the legal basis for blockchain. TLA's Blockchain Legal and Regulatory Guide offers best practice for legal practitioners working in the new technology. It is based on UK jurisdiction. The Legal Statement of the Working Group on Cryptoassets and Smart Contracts has been published for 2 years. Anne Rose and her colleagues light the way for the lawyers who decide to stay before the game.

Conclusion. As the economy recovers, we will see further increases in Law Tech adoption rates across the profession. To unlock the benefits of technology, it is necessary to shape the mind and capabilities of lawyers. Distributed Ledger technology, smart legal contracts and cryptoassets are likely to be the basis for the structure of the digital economy and future transactions. The second edition of the Blockchain Legal and Regulatory Group provides an updated framework and much-needed guidance on the use of blockchain in law.

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